

Church of St. Mamas, Palaiochora, Selino, Crete

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Entry tags: Crete, Religious Group, Byzantine, Church, Byzantine, Classical Indo-European, Indo-European, Religious Place, Language, Medieval Christianity, Monument, Graeco-Phrygian, Orthodoxy, Greek

Located a short distance inland from where the Pelekaniotikos River meets the sea just west of Palaiochora, the Church of St. Mamas is a barrel-vaulted structure with a saddle roof exterior. Restored in the 1980s, only the northern wall is original. The church is divided into two bays by a transverse arch. A large modern iconostasis divides the sanctuary from the nave however remnants of the original stone iconostasis can still be seen. In the sanctuary the northern half of the image of Christ Pantocrator is preserved in the half dome of the apse with a partially preserved halo below, likely one of the co-officiating bishops. The triumphal arch includes the image of the Mandylion in the upper register, the Archangel Gabriel from the Annunciation below, and the deacon St. Stephen in the lowest register. The Ascension can still be seen on the northern half of the barrel vault of the sanctuary next to the image of St. Melchizedek. The only remaining full figure on the transverse arch is the standing figure of Aaron who holds a flowering rod in his right hand and a vessel (in the form of the ark of Noah), a horn (typically an attribute of Samuel), and a censer in his left hand. The nave includes only the lower part of the Baptism of Christ and the Transfiguration in the upper register. In the register below are three scenes of the life of St. Mamas. These scenes include an image of St. Mamas praying, St. Mamas at the gates of Caesarea, and the Death of St. Mamas. The lower register includes an image of the enthroned Virgin. She holds the Christ child on her lap and is flanked by two angels. To the west of the Virgin is the image of St. Kyriaki. The dedicatory inscription, framed in ochre and barely legible today, is preserved to the west of St. Kyriaki above a decorative band. Based on the photographs of Giuseppe Gerola, the inscription notes that the church was built and decorated by the priest Georgios Saklos (?) and his wife and children, Photinos Abramis and his wife and children, and Georgios Abramis and his wife in 6864 (1355-56). Gerola also notes that the Abramo name can be associated with a Venetian family who settled on the island in 1211.

Date Range: 1355 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Palaiochora, Selino, Crete

Region tags: Greece, Crete

The church is located a short distance inland from where the Pelekaniotikos River meets the sea just west of Palaiochora.

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Water source

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

–Other [specify]: Single nave chapel.

↳ One single feature

– Clearing

↳ A group of structures:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

–Other [specify]: Both.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Saint Mamas

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Spatharakis, Ioannis. Dated Byzantine Wall Paintings of Crete. Leiden: Alexandros Press, 2001. See 99-100, no. 34 (with earlier bibliography)

– Source 2: Gerola, Giuseppe. Monumenti Veneti nell'isola di Creta. 4 vols. Venice: R. Istituto Veneto di Scienze, Lettere ed Arti, 1932. See Vol. IV, 440, no. 12

– Source 3: Gerola, Giuseppe, and K. Lassithiotakis. Τοπογραφικός κατάλογος των τοιχογραφημένων εκκλησιών της Κρήτης. Edited by K. Lassithiotakis. Heraklion: Εταιρία Κρητικών Ιστορικών Μελετών, 1961. See no. 115.

Notes: Detorakis, Theocharis. "Η λαϊκή λατρεία του Αγίου Μάμα στην Κρήτη." Ύδωρ εκ πέτρας 5-6 (83 1982): 111-12.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– I don't know

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

–Other [specify]: Based on the photographs of Giuseppe Gerola, the inscription notes that the church was built and decorated by the priest Georgios Saklos (?) and his wife and children, Photinos Abramis and his wife and children, and Georgios Abramis and his wife in 6864 (1355-56). Gerola also notes that the Abramo name can be associated with a Venetian family who settled on the island in 1211.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Sources and Excavations

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Topographical Context

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– Water source

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Structures Present

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– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

–Other [specify]: Both.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Saint Mamas

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

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Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– No

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– No

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– No

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– Yes

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

– 'True' fresco

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)
 - No
- ↳ Portrayals of afterlife
 - No
- ↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)
 - Yes
- ↳ Humans
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural narratives
 - Yes
- ↳ Human narratives
 - No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth
– No

↳ Sand
– No

↳ Clay
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Plaster
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Wood
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Grass
– No

|

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Plaster, brick and stone.

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

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[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]
 - Yes
- ↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:
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Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:
– Yes

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 - Yes
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- ↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)
 - No

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 - Yes
- ↳ Humans
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural narratives
 - Yes
- ↳ Human narratives
 - No

Beliefs and Practices

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is divination present:

– No

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– No

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– No

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– I don't know

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– I don't know

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– No

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– No

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– No

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: The local Archaeological Service.

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Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

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Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: The local Archaeological Service.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Church of St. Mamas, Palaiochora, Selino, Crete, Spatharakis, Ioannis. Dated Byzantine Wall Paintings of Crete. Leiden: Alexandros Press, 2001. p.99-100, no. 34

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